

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE WOOD OF *CEDRELA TOONA*, ROXB.
ISOLATION OF A LACTONE, AN ESSENTIAL OIL AND A COLOURING
MATTER

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From the wood of *Cedrela toona*, a lactone (m.p. 204°), an essential oil, and a colouring matter (m.p. 256°) have been obtained in yields of 0.40, 0.17 and 0.25% respectively

The lactone, Cedrelone, has a molecular formula $C_{25}H_{34}O_4$. It contains one ethylenic double bond, one phenolic hydroxyl, one ketonic group and a lactone ring in the molecule.

Several derivatives of Cedrelone have been prepared and analysed.

Cedrela toona, commonly known as *Tun* in Hindi, is a tall handsome tree, about 50 to 60 feet high, belonging to the natural order of Meliaceae. It is found in abundance in the sub-Himalyan tract from the Indus eastwards, Chittagong, Assam, Burma, Chota Nagpur, Western Ghats of Bombay to the Nilgris and other hills of the Indian Peninsula.

The wood, which is of a brownish red colour, has a faintly aromatic odour, mainly due to the presence of a golden yellow essential oil, and a lactone. The wood is very light and is largely used in making light furniture and musical instruments. Mell (*Text. Col.*, 1931, 53, 68) found the wood to be an interesting source of a natural dyestuff.

Besides the commercial aspects, the plant enjoys a great repute in medicine. The bark of the plant is a powerful astringent and has been used with success in chronic infantile dysentery, and as a local astringent application in various forms of ulcerations (Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Vol. 1, pp. 562-564). The infusion of the bark is given in intermittant fevers and blood complaints in Indo-China. The seeds have similar therapeutic value. The flowers are considered emmenagogue in Bombay, and are given in disordered menstruation.

The essential oil from the wood was analysed by Pillai and Sanjiva Rao (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1931, 80, 220T). By steam-distillation of the powdered wood a golden yellow pleasant smelling essential oil (yield 0.44%) was obtained. The oil was found to consist of a tricylic sesquiterpene, *l*-copaene (35%), and bicyclic hydrocarbons identified as cadinene. The sesquiterpene alcohol fraction consisted mainly of *l*-cadinol (13%).

Apart from the essential oil, no systematic work on the wood of the plant has been done by any previous worker, and in view of the great medicinal importance of the plant, the present work was undertaken to find out the active principles present and to study their constitutions.

The authors while working on the wood of the plant have isolated a pleasant smelling, heavy, essential oil, a reddish yellow colouring matter (m.p. 256°) and a lactone (m.p. 204°), in yields of 0.17%, 0.25% and 0.40% respectively on the dry wood. The systematic chemical examination of the essential oil and the colouring matter will be

the subject of separate communications ; while in the present one the lactone has been studied in detail.

The lactone, which has been named as "Cedrelone" by the authors, crystallises in colorless, glistening, rhombic needles and large hexagonal plates from benzene, melting sharply at 204°. It has a molecular formula of $C_{25}H_{30}O_6$, and contains one ethylenic double bond, one phenolic hydroxyl and one ketonic groups. Several derivatives of the compound were prepared and analysed and are described in the experimental part of the paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

For preliminary examination the powdered dry wood (25 g.) was taken in a soxhlet's apparatus and extracted with different solvents in the hot each time, for about an hour and the solvent distilled off. The following are the percentages of the extracts obtained in each case :

Water	7.47 %	$CHCl_3$	1.49 %
MeOH	17.96	CCl_4	1.08
EtOH	11.74	Benzene	1.18
Acetone	8.90	Ether	1.38
Ethyl acetate	6.06	Petrol ether	1.09

The wood on complete ignition left 2.55% of a white ash.

The air-dried, powdered wood of the plant (10.2 kg.) was extracted with hot benzene under reflux in lots of 2 kilos at a time. The extracts were filtered hot, the solvent distilled off and the viscous reddish concentrate was allowed to stand for one week, when large colorless crystals settled down. These were filtered off through a Buchner funnel and rapidly washed with ether. The mother-liquor and the washings were collected. These on concentration gave three more crops of the same crystalline compound with identical melting points. The ultimate mother-liquor was completely freed from benzene by heating on a water-bath under reduced pressure in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide, thus affording a very thick red coloured oily stuff, which was found to be the solution of the lactone in essential oil. This was treated with alcoholic potassium hydroxide on the water-bath, excess of alcohol distilled off, the mixture after cooling diluted with water, and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract on recovery of the solvent gave a heavy, pleasant smelling essential oil (yield, 0.17 %). The alkaline solution on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid precipitated the lactone, which had the same melting point as that of the original lactone, confirmed by mixed melting point when no change was noticed. The systematic work on the essential oil will be the matter of a separate communication.

The wood after extraction with benzene was further extracted with hot alcohol under reflux and the solvent distilled off when a syrupy residue was obtained. After removal of traces of the solvent by evaporation on the water-bath, the residue was extracted with hot acetone, the extract concentrated and the colouring matter precipitated with chloroform. The compound on drying was found to shrink at 215° and

melt at 254-56°. This was recrystallised from boiling glacial acetic acid in reddish yellow needles melting at 256°. On further crystallisations the melting point of the compound did not rise. Thus, 25.5 g. of the colouring matter were obtained in a yield of 0.25% on the weight of the dry wood. The colouring matter is soluble in water, alcohol, ethyl acetate and acetone, but insoluble in chloroform, petroleum ether and benzene. It dissolves in alcoholic KOH with a yellow coloration and turns red with concentrated sulphuric acid. To alcoholic ferric chloride it imparts a greenish brown coloration and with an alcoholic solution of lead acetate, a yellow precipitate is produced. Ordinarily it has got no action on Fehling's solution but only reduces it after hydrolysis, thus showing it to be a glucoside. On reduction with magnesium and methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid it turns red, thus indicating the presence of a pyrone nucleus in the molecule. It was found to contain no methoxy groups.

The various crops of the colorless crystalline matter, mentioned above, were mixed together and recrystallised from the least amount of hot benzene after treatment with animal charcoal when the compound was obtained in fine, colorless, rhombic needles and hexagonal plates melting sharply at 204°, which even after repeated crystallisation of the compound did not rise any further. Thus, 41 g. of the crystalline compound were obtained in a yield of 0.40% on the weight of the dried wood.

Cedrelone possesses a characteristic faint odour. It is soluble in benzene, chloroform, petroleum ether and acetic acid, while insoluble in cold and hot water and alcohol. It is insoluble in aqueous caustic soda and gives no coloration either on heating or prolonged standing. It is not volatile in steam and does not sublime. It dissolves in sulphuric acid (conc.) giving a deep red coloration, but on the addition of water the colour disappears and the original compound is reprecipitated. The compound gives deep yellow coloration with alcoholic caustic potash, thus definitely indicating the presence of a lactonic ring. From the alkaline solution acid precipitates the original compound. With alcoholic ferric chloride the compound gives a violet coloration showing the presence of a phenolic hydroxyl group. It fails to give Liebermann-Burchard reaction. The lactone neither gives any test with alkaline sodium nitroprusside nor reduces Tollen's reagent, a property mainly shown by $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated lactones. The compound is unsaturated and adds on bromine in benzene or acetic acid. The compound indicated the presence of no methoxyl group as found by Zeisel's method. [Found: C, 73.52; H, 7.21; M.W. (cryoscopic in phenol), 412, 415; M.W. (Rast's camphor method), 410. $C_{26}H_{30}O_5$ requires C, 73.17; H, 7.31 per cent. M.W., 410].

Repeated attempts to prepare the silver, lead and copper salts of the compound were unsuccessful.

Cedrelone Dibromide.—The compound (1.5 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (10 c.c.) and the mixture kept in a freezing mixture. To this was added a 1% solution of bromine in the same solvent in small amounts during the period of about half an hour till the bromine was in slight excess. During the addition the temperature was not allowed to rise above 0°. The mixture was kept overnight in the refrigerator, and the solvent and the excess of the bromine distilled off on the water-bath. The syrupy residue was dissolved in the minimum quantity of alcohol and a few drops of water added to the solution, when fine glistening orange needles settled down. The product was filtered,

washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol in beautiful yellow needles, m.p. 116° , yield 1.4 g. The compound is soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohols, ethyl acetate and benzene, but insoluble in hot or cold water. (Found: Br, 26.4, 28.09. $C_{26}H_{30}O_6Br$, requires Br, 28.07 per cent).

Acetylcedrelone.—The compound (2 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (10 c.c.), anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g.) added and the mixture gently refluxed in a boiling tube on a sand-bath for about 2 hours. After that the mixture was poured into cold water, well stirred and kept in the refrigerator for about 4 hours, when the acetyl derivative crystallised out in shining crystals. It was filtered and thoroughly washed with water and recrystallised from 80% alcohol in small colorless needles and plates, m.p. 148° , yield 2.01 g. The compound is soluble in alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate, benzene, ether and petrol ether, but insoluble in water. (Found: acetyl, 11.4, 10.9. $C_{27}H_{28}O_8 \cdot COCH_3$, requires acetyl, 9.51 per cent).

Cedrelone Phenylurethane.—Cedrelone (1 g.), dissolved in 5 c.c. of anhydrous benzene, was treated with phenyl isocyanate (2 g.), dissolved in 5 c.c. of the same solvent; the mixture was refluxed on the sand-bath for about 2 hours and then the solvent distilled off. The residue was allowed to cool when it became a syrup. This was dissolved in absolute alcohol and allowed to stand for some time when shining long needles melting at 232° were obtained. The compound is soluble in alcohol, benzene, ether and petrol-ether but insoluble in water. (Found: N, 2.32. $C_{25}H_{30}O_4 \cdot OCONHC_6H_5$, requires N, 2.64 per cent).

Cedrelone Monoxime.—Hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.5 g.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (3 g.) were thoroughly mixed together in a mortar and the mixture was taken in 25 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and heated for about half an hour on the sand-bath. To this was added cedrelone (3 g.) and the mixture was refluxed in a boiling tube for about an hour on a sand-bath. The mixture while hot was poured into cold water, when a crystalline mass settled down. It was filtered, thoroughly washed with water, dried and recrystallised from hot alcohol in shining colorless prisms and needles, m.p. 258° , yield 1.46 g. The compound is soluble in alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate, but insoluble in water, ether and petrol-ether. (Found: N, 3.18. $C_{25}H_{30}O_4 \cdot NOH$, requires N, 3.29 per cent).

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